

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Abstract

The EU aims to enhance soil health for food security and climate change mitigation. This report explores three business models—public payments for ecosystem services, carbon credit markets, and value chain payments for ecosystem services—to remunerate farmers. It examines the legislative framework and summarizes articles on factors relevant for farmers to engage in these business models. The report identifies public payments and value chain payments as the most promising models. Public payments are a primary funding source, while value chain payments gain traction due to companies' interest in achieving climate neutrality by 2050. However, limited research on farmers' preferences for value chain payments is available. For the business model based on carbon credit markets, soil health measures on arable land face challenges to meet the long-term storage requirements necessary for EU carbon credit certification. Researchers interested in carbon markets should therefore focus on farmers' acceptance of contracts involving agroforestry, afforestation, or peatland rewetting.

Executive summary

The EU seeks to promote soil health measures to secure food provision and to mitigate climate change. Soil health measures require adjustments in farm management and farmers usually expect a remuneration to implement them. This report reviews the existing literature on business models and social innovations that seek to promote soil health. The report considers three business models: i) public payments for ecosystem services ii) carbon credit markets and iii) value chain payments for ecosystem services. The report first describes the underlying legislative framework of the business models. Next, it summarizes what is known about the business models' performance (e.g., soil health parameters, co-benefits for sustainability) and factors decisive for farmers' preferences for the business models. Last, the potential success of the business models is evaluated based on the literature review.

The business models of public payments for ecosystem services and value chain payments for ecosystem services are identified as the most promising alternatives. Public payments are important as payments through the CAP are the most important funding source. Furthermore, farmers seem to prefer action-based governmental payments above result-based payments through carbon markets. Value chain payments hold potential because the interest of companies to offer payments through the value chain may strongly increase as larger companies must reach climate neutrality by 2050. However, only few articles elicit farmers' preferences for value chain payments so far.

For the business model based on carbon credit markets it was found that soil health measures on arable land can increase soil organic carbon, but that they hold a high risk of reversibility. Therefore, soil health measures are unlikely to fulfil the long-term storage requirements that are required for EU carbon credit certification. Researchers interested in this business model should consider focusing on farmers' acceptance for contracts that demand agroforestry, afforestation, or peatland rewetting. However, research on farmers' preferences indicates that long contract durations are unlikely to be accepted by farmers, and that farmers are less willing to apply the measures that appear more suitable for carbon credit certification. Therefore, incentivizing farmers to engage in carbon markets might be challenging.

1 Introduction

Under the new common agricultural policy (CAP) the European Union (EU) aims to improve the sustainability of our food system (European Commission, 2023b). Soils are the basis of the food system; they provide nutrients, water, oxygen and support to plants. However, the quality of soils in the EU – as described by the soil organic matter content and soil biodiversity – is declining. This decline is due to human activities that cause over-fertilization, compaction, or contamination (European Commission, 2018).

Healthy soils are not only important for the food system, but they are also providing various other ecosystem services. They can, for instance, store carbon and thus help to mitigate the effects of global warming. Topsoils in the EU, for instance, store 14 billion tons of carbon, which is equivalent to 51 billion tonnes of CO₂ equivalents. This is much more than what is annually emitted by the member states (European Commission, 2018). It is even believed that adjustments in farm management practices can result in additional carbon sequestration. Healthy soils can, therefore, help to reach the Paris Agreement, where the EU set the goal of reaching climate neutrality by 2050 (European Commission, 2023b).

In general, carbon farming describes all activities where farmers and land users deliver the following outcomes i) carbon removal and storage of carbon in biomass or soils, ii) the avoidance of future CO₂ and Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions or iii) the reduction of existing CO₂ and GHG emissions (McDonald et al., 2021). Examples of carbon farming practices include:

1. Afforestation and reforestation
2. Agroforestry and other forms of mixed farming
3. Soil health measures on arable land (for instance, reduced tillage, cover crops, improved fertilizer planning, arable land conversion to grassland)
4. Rewetting and restoration of peatlands

Research shows that farmers can be financially incentivised to apply soil health measures using public payments (e.g., Schaub et al., 2023; Schulze et al., 2023) or private payments (e.g., Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Mamine et al., 2020; Weituschat et al., 2023). The project NOVASOIL aims to promote soil health measures by identifying potential business models for farmers that allow remuneration for the implementation of soil health practices. Since soil health measures can potentially lead to carbon sequestration, carbon credit markets are identified as one potential business model. Besides this, soil health measures can also be funded by the EU through the eco-schemes or agri-environmental schemes (AES) (COWI et al., 2021). Furthermore, private incentives such as payments over the value chain for environmentally friendly production might hold potential. This report outlines what is known in the grey and the academic literature on factors relevant for the success of these three business models before discussing their potential.

This review first outlines the conceptual framework of the analysis (section 2). Then the legislative framework relevant for the three business models is summarized (section 3). In section 4, peer-reviewed and un-peer-reviewed articles on farmers' and land users' acceptance for payments through the three business models are presented.

Section 5 holds information on the carbon farming activities themselves. In section 6, the findings are discussed.

2 Conceptual framework - soil health promoting business models

One of the objectives of NOVASOIL is to identify promising business models to promote soil health. In general, a 'business model' outlines how a company operates, creates, delivers, and captures value (Gupta & Gupta, 2022).

Three business models will be considered, **public payments for ecosystem services**, payments through the **value chain**, where farmers receive a payment for a product that also fulfils certain environmental requirements, and **carbon markets** that organise the trade of carbon credits. Carbon credits are certified 'carbon removal units', where one unit represents one tonne of certified net carbon removal (McDonald et al., 2021).¹

A report for the European Union (EU) also distinguishes between these three possible business models for soil health. When it comes to analysing the potential success of the business models, it remarks for the business model based on public payments, that increasing the CAP's climate and environmental effectiveness should be a priority when researching on the business model. In addition, it highlights for the private business models (value chain and carbon markets) that it needs to be ensured that carbon reductions are not overstated, and instead transparently monitored, reported, and verified (MRV requirement). In addition, the authors advise controlling whether the business models can deliver the expected socio-environmental co-benefits to society, and socio-economic benefits to farmers (McDonald et al., 2021).

The conceptual framework in deliverable 1.1 of the NOVASOIL project identifies the following success factors for soil health business models: costs and benefits, acceptance, environmental effectiveness, compliance with the legal framework and fairness for the involved parties.

¹ In the conceptual framework from WPI, a fourth business model was described. It refers to the collective implementation of actions. Within this review, we consider collective implementation approaches as sub-types of AES or private approaches (carbon credit trade and value chain payments). Furthermore, social innovations are not addressed separately. Social innovation is a process. It describes the creation and execution of new solutions involving conceptual, process, product, or organizational changes to address socio-economic and environmental challenges (OECD, 2023). Therefore, the business models themselves can be products of social innovation processes.

3 Legislative framework

Below, the legislative framework that needs to be fulfilled to receive public or private payments for ecosystem services and the draft regulation 2018/841 for EU carbon credit certification are summarized.

3.1 Public funding - Payments for ecosystem services over the CAP

Public funding for environmentally friendly farm management is granted over the CAP. Payments for ecosystem services can either be financed through Pillar i) the European Agriculture Guarantee Fund (EAGF) or Pillar ii) the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). These two funding pillars lead to payment schemes with different characteristics. Payments granted over the first pillar are, for example, annual, while payments granted over the second pillar are multi-annual. In addition, the second pillar payments are co-financed by the member states (European Commission, 2023a).

The budget shares of the first and second pillar are not fixed, meaning that the shares are not the same across member states. Within certain limits, the member states can transfer budget between the two pillars. Overall, eleven states allocated budgets from the first to the second pillar. Politicians from Portugal, Poland, Malta, Luxemburg, and Hungary seem to prefer first pillar payments, while politicians from Slovakia, Romania, Netherlands, Latvia, Italia, France, Greece, Germany, Denmark, Czechia, Belgium allocated more budget to the second pillar. Next to the payments, member states can provide additional national funding. Overall, more than 11 billion Euros will be available to fund practices related to environment, climate, and animal welfare in the current CAP period (European Commission, 2023a).

Farmers must comply with certain conditions to receive payments from the first and second pillar. The so-called ‘enhanced conditionality’ consists of statutory management requirements that aim at sustainable farming. Farmers receive direct payments from the first pillar for measures that lead to some ecosystem services. The measures of the ‘enhanced conditionality’ aim at good agricultural and environmental conditions (GAEC) and are shown in table 1. Many of the measures already aim to improve soil health, even though some have different primary objectives. GAEC 9, for instance, is strongly oriented towards biodiversity (European Commission, 2023a).

TABLE 1 GAEC REQUIREMENTS UNDER THE SO-CALLED ENHANCED CONDITIONALITY (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2023A)

GAEC	Measures
GAEC 1	Permanent grassland (ratio of grassland may not fall by more than 5% at national level)
GAEC 2	Protection of wetland and peatland (carbon rich soils)
GAEC 3	Ban on burning arable stubble
GAEC 4	Buffer strips along water courses
GAEC 5	Tillage management
GAEC 6	Minimum soil cover
GAEC 7	Crop rotation
GAEC 8	Non-productive area and features (4% at farm level)
GAEC 9	Ban on converting and ploughing permanent grasslands in Natura 2000 sites

Especially GAEC 2 reflects the growing interest of the commission in combating climate change through changes in soil management. Under the measures, the full drainage of peat- and wetlands is restricted, as well as tillage, ploughing, extraction and the burning of peat. Which additional GAEC measures apply can also vary by country. Countries can demand stricter requirements that, for instance, build on the pre-defined GAECs (European Commission, 2023a).

3.1.1 Payments granted over the first pillar (eco-schemes)

Schemes for the climate, the environment, and animal welfare (Eco-schemes) are new tools to deliver the goals set by the European Commission. Eco-schemes must account for at least 25% of the budget under the first pillar. Practices can only qualify to become eco-schemes when they require management adjustments that go beyond the legislative requirements, and the enhanced conditionality (European Commission, 2023a). The member states are obliged to include at least one eco-scheme in their strategic implementation plans (Eurostat, 2023). When deciding upon the eco-scheme(s), the member states were free to choose management requirements that best fulfil the specific needs of their countries (Eurostat, 2023). Thus, the implementation may strongly vary across countries.

As an example of the variation across countries, two summaries are provided of how eco-scheme payments are implemented in Germany and the Netherlands. In the Netherlands, eco-schemes are implemented using a result-based point system. In the Dutch system, each activity converts into eco-points. They reflect the activities' impact on different environmental objectives (climate, air and soil, water, landscape, biodiversity). The eco-points translate into hectare payments when farmers achieve enough points in total. Farmers can either use one eco-scheme with a high impact or multiple ones with lower ambitions to reach an entry level threshold and to qualify for a payment for all hectares of the farm. If they want to achieve higher payments, multiple measures referring to different objectives need to be combined to reach higher thresholds. There are three threshold levels: bronze (€ 60/ha for all hectares of the farm), silver (€ 100/ha for all hectares of the farm) and gold (€ 200/ha for all hectares of the farm) (Jongeneel & Gonzalez-Martinez, 2023).

Dutch farmers can use a simulation tool to evaluate the effect of combinations of multiple eco-schemes. The tool calculates the overall points achieved and the level of payments that are granted for the mix of measures. The eco-schemes to choose from under the air and soil objective or climate are 'grass/clover', 'grassland with herbs', 'permanent pasture', 'perennial cultivation', 'wet cultivation', 'crop rotation', 'nitrogen fixating crops and protein', 'green cover', 'early harvesting of root crops no later than August', 'extended grazing during day', 'extended grazing during night', 'buffer strips with herbs on arable land', 'green fallows', 'wooden banks' and 'organic farming' (Jongeneel & Gonzalez-Martinez, 2023).

In contrast to the Netherlands, Germany rewards all farmers with the same amount of payments for the eco-schemes they choose. Farmers can choose between seven eco-schemes. The first is aiming at improvements of biodiversity and habitat conservation.

Farmers interested in the scheme have actions to choose from (e.g., additional non-productive land on arable land, or planting flower strips on arable land). The second eco-scheme is the provision of more diverse crops (at least 10% legumes); the third is maintaining agroforestry; the fourth is the extensification of permanent grassland; the fifth is result-oriented extensive management on grassland; the sixth is no use of chemical synthetic pesticides and the protection of Natura 2000 sites. The seventh is adjusted farm management in Natura 2000 areas (Scheid & Ittner, 2022). The amount of payments farmers receive depends on the area provided for the schemes. For instance, farmers participating in the eco-scheme 'non-productive arable land', receive 1300 €/ha for the 1% of farmland they set aside. If they set aside more than 1% of farmland, they receive only 500 €/ha for the additional land (Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Ernährung, 2023). Overall, the two examples from the Netherlands and Germany highlight that the mode of implementation of the eco-schemes can strongly differ across member states. An overview of the implementation across 15 member states is provided in Runge et al. (2022).

3.1.2 Payments granted over the second pillar (AES)

Eco-schemes provide incentives for softer management restrictions, while other, more demanding measures are financed from the second pillar of the CAP. These measures include agri-environment-climate commitments, forest-environment-climate commitments, agroforestry, afforestation, and the conversion to and maintenance of organic farming (European Commission, 2023a).² We will refer to contracts financing these measures as AES. Measures financed over the second pillar are multi-annual as the environmental goals require longer and more complex engagement (Guyomard et al., 2023). The contracts usually cover five years (European Commission, 2023a).

Comparing two countries, Netherlands and Germany, it can be shown that large differences can also be found in the AES implementation. The Netherlands chose a collective implementation approach. Since 2016, farmer collectives have been responsible for the implementation of AES. The approach is believed to motivate farmers, to enhance the special coordination of measures (Barghusen et al., 2021), and to lower error rates in the application process (Terwan, 2016). In practice farmer collectives first formulate a management strategy with the local government, before setting up private contracts with farmers (Barghusen et al., 2021). Farmers are approached by the collectives when their area holds potential to contribute to a specific environmental objective. The collective will also suggest concrete measures that the farmers can implement (personal communication with a Dutch collective).

In contrast, German farmers apply individually to participate in AES and select a scheme themselves. The schemes vary across the German states to take regional-specific aspects into consideration (Guyomard et al., 2023). An important difference with the eco-schemes, where farmers are entitled to the payment, is that farmers can indicate their interest in AES via their application but may not be able to participate. This can happen when too many farmers apply, and the scheme's budget would be exceeded. Some farmers are then informed that participation will not be possible, and

² Since the introduction of the new CAP, organic farming can now be supported by a mix of payments from the second pillar (maintenance payment) and from the first pillar (a payment made for conversion).

funding is only provided to farmers that are located in areas that are considered to create higher ecological value (BMEL, 2023).

3.1.3 Action-based vs. result-based payments for ecosystem services

Most of the German AES and eco-schemes offer so-called action-based payments apart from the eco-scheme 'result-oriented extensive management on grassland', which is a result-based payment. This means the payment depends on the presence of certain indicator species (Bayerisches Staatsministerium für Ernährung, 2023).

Generally, a scheme is considered action-based when it rewards the required measures (e.g., a ban of chemical fertilisation or pesticides). The amount of payment is usually based on the average income forgone when implementing the practice (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). The payments do not differentiate between different farmers even though farmers might face different opportunity costs (e.g., Schaub et al., 2023). In contrast to this, a scheme is considered result-based when the reward is based on the achievement of a desired output (e.g., the number of species found on grassland). Result-based schemes do not remunerate specific practices and farmers can choose the measures that they apply freely (Herzon et al., 2018).

Action-based payments have the advantage of being more straightforward to monitor compared to result-based schemes. Farmers may prefer this approach because it ensures consistent payments. However, Bartkowski et al. (2021) and Burton & Schwarz (2013) argue that uniform payments across farmers and a lack of alignment with specific goals, such as enhancing biodiversity or carbon sequestration, lead to inefficiencies.

Result-based schemes can enhance the effectiveness of the schemes. First, only farmers that are confident to deliver the desired results will participate in a result-based scheme (Bartkowski et al., 2021). Second, farmers are expected to view the desired environmental outcome as a product and strive to achieve it cost-effectively by selecting the most suitable management practices for specific outcomes (Matzdorf et al., 2008). This approach can enhance both environmental and cost-effectiveness also by considering regional conditions more comprehensively (Burton & Schwarz, 2013; Zabel & Roe, 2009).

Hybrid schemes seek to overcome the disadvantages of purely result-based and purely action-based schemes. In hybrid schemes, part of the payment is fixed and based on the measures applied. In addition, hybrid schemes grant bonus payments when certain results are reached (Herzon et al., 2018). Hybrid and result-based payments are preferred over action-based payments by the European Commission, even though current payments for ecosystem services are still mostly action-based (COWI et al., 2021).

3.2 Private initiatives - Carbon markets for credits with EU certification

Currently, the regulative framework (regulation 2018/841) of the European Commission (2022b) for voluntary carbon credit certification is in its development. The regulation seeks to ensure a high quality of carbon removals by establishing a certification and registration system that avoids greenwashing. Therefore, it defines carbon removals, and outline which activities ensure carbon removals, and how the verification and monitoring should take place (European Commission, 2022a). Information from the draft of regulation 2018/841 is summarized below.

3.2.1 The Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y criteria

The regulation sets out the requirements under which carbon removals should be eligible for certification. Carbon removal activities³ need to meet the **Q.U.A.L.I.T.Y** criteria (which stands for quantification, additionality, long-term storage, and sustainability). The quality criteria summarize the requirements for the removals: to allow certification carbon removals should be **quantified** in an accurate and robust way, they should generate a net carbon removal benefit that is **additional**, they should ensure **long-term storage of carbon** and have a neutral impact or a co-benefit for other **sustainability** objectives (European Commission, 2022b).

3.2.2 Quantification & additionality

Overall, carbon removals should be quantified in a relevant, accurate, complete, consistent, and comparable manner. Third-party auditing is intended to ensure the credibility and reliability of the carbon removals and is necessary to meet the **quantification** requirement. For the quantification, the net carbon removal benefit should be computed following two steps: First, operators⁴ should quantify the gross amount of additional carbon removals that a carbon removal activity has generated in comparison to a baseline. It is stated that so-called standardized baselines should be used. These reflect the standard performance of comparable activities in similar social, economic, environmental, and technological circumstances and geographical locations (European Commission, 2022b).

Standardized baselines should ensure objectivity, minimize compliance and other administrative costs, and positively recognize the action of first movers who have already engaged in carbon removal activities. For the future, the use of available digital technologies (e.g., electronic databases and geographic information systems, remote sensing, artificial intelligence and machine learning, and electronic maps) should be promoted to decrease the costs of defining standardized baselines and to allow monitoring carbon removal activities individually (European Commission, 2022b).

³ Carbon removal activities are all human activities that allow capturing CO₂ from the atmosphere and ensure long-term storage, for instance, in geological reservoirs, terrestrial and marine ecosystems, or in products.

⁴ The operator (or group of operators)⁴ is expected to support the certification body during certification and recertification audits, notably by giving access to the activity premises and providing any required data and documentation. The list of accredited certification bodies shall be made publicly available in the European Union registry.

Second, for quantifying the net carbon removal any increase in greenhouse gas emissions related to the implementation of the carbon removal activity should be deducted. Relevant greenhouse gas emissions can occur from the use of more fertilizers, chemicals, fuel or energy, and indirect emissions can occur from changes in practices. In case that a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, besides CO₂, results from the implementation of the carbon removal activity, this decrease should not be considered in the carbon removal. Instead, these emission reductions should be considered as a co-benefit for sustainability (European Commission, 2022b).

To ensure beneficial effects for the overall emissions, carbon removal activities should be **additional**. Therefore, activities should go beyond statutory requirements meaning that operators should carry out activities that are not already imposed upon them by the applicable law (European Commission, 2022). In essence, this means that the standardized baseline for farmers needs to reflect the carbon emissions of farms that comply with the given legislative framework.

The quantification process is still in its development. Comparing the potential carbon removal activities that are the most mature, those that have the largest potential for carbon storage and, in the case of carbon farming activities, those that have the largest potential to provide positive co-benefits for biodiversity will be prioritised. Currently, carbon storage in peat soils, reforestation and agroforestry are believed to be the most promising alternatives (McDonald et al., 2021).

3.2.3 Long term storage & liability

Carbon storage should ideally mean that the removals are permanent. Permanent carbon storage means that the captured carbon is stored for centuries. This is, for example, through geological storage and carbon mineralization. However, different types of carbon removal activities vary in terms of the removal process, the storage medium and the timescales of the storage. Therefore, carbon farming or storage in certain wood products achieves long-term carbon removals that usually covers decades. However, also these long-term removals are assumed to contribute to meeting climate goals (European Commission, 2022b).

To ensure that storage is permanent or long-term, operators are required to take relevant preventive measures to mitigate risks of stored carbon being released back into the atmosphere. Because of this, the monitoring period should cover the whole period over which carbon storage is guaranteed, and the validity of the certified carbon removals should depend on the expected duration of the storage. At the end of the monitoring period, the carbon can be assumed to be released into the atmosphere, unless the economic operator proves differently. In addition, appropriate liability mechanisms should be introduced to address cases of reversal. Such mechanisms may include the discounting of carbon removal units, collective buffers, and insurance mechanisms (European Commission, 2022b).

3.2.4 Co-benefits for sustainability

Carbon farming is assumed to have the potential to not only mitigate climate change but also to deliver co-benefits for sustainability. Therefore, minimum sustainability requirements will be introduced. These should ensure that carbon removal activities

have at least a neutral impact or even generate co-benefits for other sustainability objectives (e.g., biodiversity, protection of water and marine resources, pollution prevention). The minimum sustainability requirements mean that practices, such as forest monocultures that produce harmful effects for biodiversity should not be eligible for certification (European Commission, 2022b).

Operators can report co-benefits that contribute to the sustainability objectives beyond the minimum sustainability requirement. These additional co-benefits are expected to give more economic value to the certified carbon removals and to result in higher revenues for the operators. Therefore, the carbon removal certificate should also indicate whether a carbon removal activity has a positive or a neutral impact. Certification methodologies for these aspects also need to be further developed to use the full potential of carbon farming (European Commission, 2022b).

3.2.5 Carbon certificates & trade of carbon credits

A public registry for carbon credits will be established. The registry should contain the documents resulting from the certification process (e.g., information on certification audits), the certificates, and a log of transactions. This way transparency, full traceability of carbon removal certificates should be ensured. This is considered necessary to avoid the risk of fraud and double counting. Fraud may occur if more than one certificate is issued for the same carbon removal activity, for instance, when the activity has been registered under two different third parties. Fraud may also occur when the same certificate is used several times (European Commission, 2022b).

As an example, information on how verification is organised in the USA can be found on the websites of the Climate Action Reserve (CAR) or the American Carbon Registry. The CAR protocol, for instance, refers to a standardised farm-based baseline and has additionality requirements. Regarding the information provided, it should be noted that the carbon market in the USA is also still under development (Canales et al., 2024).

3.3 Private initiatives - value chain payments

Contracts can also be between stakeholders of the value chain (e.g., supermarkets or processors) and farmers. The CONSOLE project (GA 817949) conducted a literature review and an online search for existing public and private funding schemes for environmental outcomes in the Netherlands. The authors show that more than 50% of the contracts are either completely private (between value chain actors and farmers) or funded by a combination of private and public funding (public-private funding) (Harmanny & Schulp, 2023).

It can be expected that the interest of private companies to engage with farmers to ensure better environmental protection will even grow. This is because the directive on corporate social responsibility due diligence requires larger companies to better ensure that their production strategy is in line with environmental conventions. More specifically, companies with a turnover of more than 150 million euros must ensure that their production practices are in line with the Paris agreement (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). This highlights the importance of private contracts and shows that their potential to achieve improvements in soil health should not be underestimated.

In general, contracts present binding agreements between two parties that can be natural or legislative entities (e.g., companies are legislative parties). They are usually based on national-specific frameworks and touch on multiple areas of law (e.g., public and private law), but can also touch on EU-specific regulations such as the CAP or even international regulations (e.g., trade agreements). Contracts provide the parties with a certain degree of legal certainty (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). Furthermore, contracts usually have requirements for essential aspects (*essentialia negotii*). For instance, according to Dutch law, contracts usually need to have information on contract duration, notice periods, delivery, consequences when commitments are not fulfilled, terms of payment and collection, warranty, handling of disputes, maintenance, and service agreements. Contracts are also valid in an oral format; nevertheless, written agreements should be preferred (Netherlands Chamber of Commerce, 2023).

Contracts can be standardised with the same agreement for multiple parties, or they can be individual (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). Value chain contracts for the provision of ecosystem services, which include environmental aspects, are often production contracts, where farmers agree to deliver a product that was produced under certain standards. Payments for environmental aspects are usually not granted separately but are granted via a higher product price. In addition to higher prices, farmers are often provided with a purchase guarantee and sales guarantee for certain volumes of product. The downstream value chain actor (e.g., a supermarket) will usually cover the higher costs by selling the product at higher prices to consumers (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). To avoid that farmers are not sufficiently compensated and that other actors of the food supply chain exploit their market positions, a proposal for an EU regulation for sustainable food labelling is foreseen for 2024 (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). To avoid that consumers are being misled in their purchase decisions, the EU seeks to ban greenwashing and unsupported claims. The use of claims such as 'eco-friendly', 'climate-neutral' or 'climate-friendly' will be forbidden from 2026 on when companies cannot prove via approved certification schemes that their off-sets and biodiversity contributions are real (European Parliament, 2023).

The above-described production contracts can be classified as a vertical contractual agreement. However, horizontal contractual agreements for farmers' initiatives may present an alternative option. These collective approaches can help to overcome issues of market power between farmers and other actors in the food supply chain. When farmers produce and sell sustainable products together, this can help to achieve better profitability of sustainable production (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). In addition, farmers can also attempt to sell their products via the short food supply chain and promote them with claims (Demeyer et al., 2022).

A real-life example of payments over the value chain is the Barilla sustainable farming project that is strongly focused on soil health. The project seeks to get more farmers to supply strategic input materials such as durum wheat, common wheat, eggs, and tomatoes that are produced under Barilla's sustainable agriculture code. Farmers agreeing to the production requirements receive price premiums. Suppliers committing to the code voluntarily agree to comply with adjusted farming practices to lower negative impacts on the environment. Soil health measures, such as crop rotation and adjustments in tillage, are part of Barilla's requirements. Furthermore,

Barilla strives for a more efficient production, for instance, through lower input use. To support farmers in achieving improvements, Barilla offers online decision support tools and training. To ensure that their training efforts pay off, Barilla prefers long-term contracts. To provide certainty to all parties, all agreements with Barilla are set down in written contracts (Barilla, 2022; Global Compact, 2015).

Some earlier projects, like the Interreg carbon farming project, have already set-up initiatives for carbon credit trade. The final report of the project provides information on these initiatives. It appears that the initiatives can be classified as payments over the value chain rather than trials of carbon markets. The buyers, such as municipalities, were identified beforehand. The initiatives often had short runtimes for the contracts (e.g., three years), and were strongly focused on soil health measures. Furthermore, the offered carbon prices were relatively high (€52 per ton) (Demeyer et al., 2022).

As mentioned, farmers can also attempt to sell environmentally friendly products directly to consumers, for instance, via the short food supply chain. A novel start-up even attempts to promote the sale of the environmentally friendly practice and the resulting ecosystem service itself. The online platform agro natura offers private nature protection certificates to interested consumers (e.g., citizens and companies). Over the certificates buyers can, for instance, protect peatlands, meadows or old fruit trees (Agro Natura, 2024).

4 Factors relevant for farmers' acceptance of soil health business models

Three different soil health business models are analysed during the project. Therefore, three separate literature searches on farmers' acceptance for these business models were conducted and are discussed in this section.

4.1 Method

This report aims to identify factors relevant to the success of the different business models. Potential success can be reflected in farmers' acceptance. Therefore, the majority of the reviewed articles use Discrete Choice Experiments (DCE).

DCE elicit how participants (n) choose between different, discrete alternatives (j). It is assumed that a participant chooses the alternative that provides the highest utility (U_{nj}) to him or her. The utility of the alternative depends on the k -attributes of the alternative and characteristics of the decision-maker, both denoted in the vector (x_{jk}). Their influence on the utility is described by the coefficients (β_k) (Hensher et al., 2015):

$$U_{nj} = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k x_{njkr} + \varepsilon_{nj} \quad (1)$$

Therefore, DCE can provide information on which attributes and characteristics were identified as being influential for farmers' decisions to accept contracts. Articles that do not include DCE are not included in the overview in table 1. However, their findings were added into the results descriptions to provide deeper insights.

For the article search, the following keywords, and different combinations were included: discrete choice, farmers' preferences, carbon credits, agri-environmental schemes, payments for ecosystem services, soil health, regenerative farm practices,

peatland rewetting, agroforestry, afforestation, and contract farming. Research on farmers' preferences for business models including soil health measures appears to be quite limited. Therefore, articles on afforestation, agroforestry, and peatland rewetting were also included. This review includes articles from Europe and the USA. The covered countries are stated to have comparable experiences with AES (Schaub et al., 2023).

Numerous review articles already present overviews on factors relevant for farmers' decision for the adoption of sustainable farming practices. Their findings and classifications were used to structure the tables in this literature review.

Dessart et al. (2019) reviewed literature from the past 20 years on behavioural factors that are relevant for farmers' decision to implement sustainable practices linked to biodiversity, water, soil and landscape improvements. In addition to behavioural factors, Schaub et al. (2023) included opportunity costs and contractual features. Furthermore, two review articles focus on contractual features in detail. Schulze et al. (2023) analysed articles with DCE on farmers' preferences for contracts that include land use prescriptions, and other contractual features. Mamine et al. (2020) mostly analyse the quality of DCEs but also present an overview of various contractual features. In addition to these reviews, Buck & Palumbo-Compton (2022) present a recent overview of factors that are important for farmers' decision to participate in carbon sequestration. They focus on what is known about farmers' preferences for certain business models (e.g., governmental payments and carbon markets), and on farmers' preferences for financial incentives and the role of sustainable co-benefits. In comparison to the mentioned review articles, this article tries to distinguish between articles on farmers' preferences for public payments (AES), and private initiatives (carbon credit trade and payments over the value chain).

4.2 Results – Research found on the different business models

Table 2 provides an overview of the articles that were included in the analysis. The research was mostly conducted in Europe (19), while six articles focus on North America. The articles cover a period of 17 years (2007 – 2024). Fourteen of the included articles refer to farmers' preferences for **AES**, seven articles are on their preferences for carbon credit markets (**CM**) and five are on value chain payments (**VCP**) for soil health measures. Looking at the measures, eighteen articles feature soil health measures, three feature agroforestry or afforestation, and two are about peatland rewetting.

An important finding is that only one article strongly focuses on contracts by value chain actors for soil friendly production practices. Weituschat et al. (2023) focus on farmers' willingness to engage in Barilla's sustainable farming initiative, that was briefly introduced in section 3.3. Participating farmers receive a price premium. However, their analysis strongly focusses on the measures demanded and not on the relationship between farmers and the value chain actor. Beharry-Borg et al. (2013) is also in the VCP category. It analyses farmers' preferences for contracts from water providers to reduce fertilizer usage. The article's primary focus is not on soil health even though reductions in chemical fertilizers improve soil quality.

Some of the articles do not exclusively refer to one business model. Salazar-Ordóñez et al. (2021) was added to the AES and the VCP category. This article focuses on farmers'

willingness to engage in AES for soil health friendly olive oil production. In their discussion, the possibility of eco-labelling is addressed, even though it is not what the article mainly focuses on. Häfner & Piorr (2021) analyse farmers' preferences for peatland rewetting. One of their attributes is that a delivery contract of the produced grassland to a bioenergy production plant exists. Their article is, therefore, classified to be in the AES and the VCP category. Stetter & Sauer (2022) analyse farmers' willingness to pick a contract for agroforestry. Agroforestry is not often used in Bavaria. In their attributes, information is provided on the margins of the systems, the wood is described to be used for bioenergy. Since they indirectly refer to margins that might be achieved over value chain activities, their article was also assumed to touch on two business models. These last two articles show that value chains can be used to incentivise farmers also in different ways than described in section 3.3. Section 3.3 focused primarily on the remuneration of ecosystem services, but the articles show that new products can also emerge from an adjusted way of farm management.

Two articles analyse farmers' preferences for soil health measures and whether these should be financed using public payments or over carbon markets. Canales et al. (2024) investigate farmers' preferences for the application of soil health measures in the US. They find that public payments were preferred over carbon markets. Gramig & Widmar (2018) find the same result when US farmers were offered contracts demanding reduced tillage. Barbato & Strong (2023) confirm this and find in their interviews that farmers would rather not implement the measures when payments are result-based and not secured. The two DCEs, Gramig & Widmar (2018) and Canales et al. (2024), were also sorted in two categories, AES and CM.

Furthermore, multiple articles on carbon markets feature fixed payments (e.g., Aslam et al., 2017, Shaikh et al., 2007). The articles do not specify where the fixed amount comes from. Given that carbon markets in theory operate as result-based schemes, having a fixed amount of payment means that either public (AES) or private payments (coming from the value chain) might be needed in addition to be able to offer fixed payments.

Furthermore, one article could not be classified, it included soil health measures as mandatory to qualify for crop insurance. Jørgensen et al. (2020) asked farmers to choose for or against a traditional market-based crop insurance coupled with the application of soil health measures. Changes in cropping were assumed to serve as a natural insurance against climate change. This article also displays that incentives exist additionally to the three business models.

TABLE 2 DETAILS ON THE INCLUDED ARTICLES THAT USE DCES

Study	Country	Business Modell	Measures
Aslam et al., (2017)	UK	CM	Set aside (grassland, afforestation), grazing, and restrictions of ploughing
Assaker (2023)	Italy	CM	Soil health measures (not included in detail)
Barreiro-Hurlé et al. (2010)	Spain	AES	Various - some addressing soil health (e.g. keeping stubble, limitations in pesticides, cultivation requirements certain crops / crop rotations, conservation tillage)
Beharry-Borg et al. (2013)	UK	VCP	Restrictions for chemical and organic fertilizers
Canales et al. (2024)	US	AES/CM	Restriction for tillage, cover crop and crop rotation requirements, requirements to use side specific information to reduce inputs (e.g., fertilizer)
Cheye (2023)	US	CM	Free of choice (conservation tillage, rangeland management, conversion of arable land, tree planting)
Dickinson et al. (2012)	US	CM	Sequestration in wood (enforced over a forest management plan)
Gramig and Widmar (2018)	US	AES / CM	No-till, conservation tillage
Häfner & Piorr (2021)	Germany	AES / VCP	Rewetting of peatland (high water levels and production of grass for biogas power plant)
Jaeck & Lifran, (2014)	France	AES	Weeding strategy (mechanical weeding, different intensities pesticide usage), crop rotation, growing periods
Jørgensen et al. (2020)	Denmark	n.a. (Insurance)	Reduction of tillage, mulching of plant residues that serves as a natural insurance
Lapierre et al. (2023)	France	AES	Intercropping and pesticide restrictions in vineyards
Latacz-Lohmann et al. (2019)	Germany	AES	Rewetting of peatland (water levels, restrictions on fertilizer usage and grassland renewal)
Levers et al. (2021)	US	AES	Alternative cropping systems (cultivation of perennial crops)
Niskanen et al. (2021)	Finland	AES	Grazing times, share of perennial crops, decrease requirement nitrogen surpluses
Salazar-Ordóñez et al. (2021)	Spain	AES / VCP	Cover crops and cover crop management, pesticide restrictions
Schulz et al. (2014)	Germany	n.a.	Greening measures (e.g., ecological focus area, crop rotation)
Shaikh et al. (2007)	Canada	CM	Afforestation on marginal farmland
Stetter & Sauer (2022)	Germany	AES/VCP	Agroforestry
Trenholm et al. (2017)	Canada	AES	Land conversion to meadow, trees or wetlands
Villanueva et al. (2017)	Spain	AES	Cover crop area, cover crop management (no pesticides, no till), inclusion ecological focus areas
Weituschat et al. (2023)	Italy	VCP	Legumes in crop rotation, flower strips, glyphosate restrictions
Zandersen et al. (2016)	Denmark	AES	Reduced tillage, usage of clean sludge

4.2.1 Important contractual features

Table 3 has information on contractual features that were identified to be relevant for the acceptance of soil health business models in the existing literature. The structure of the table is based on Mamine et al. (2020). Mamine et al. (2020) show that a large variety of incentives and commitments exist. Incentives are assumed to have a positive effect, while commitments are assumed to impact the predicted probability to choose a contract, negatively.

Across all articles on the different business models, most feature a fixed payment per hectare and year, or an expected income per hectare and year. This also applies to articles in the carbon markets category. The willingness-to-accept measures estimated in these articles display farmers' compensation requirements and were used to compare them to carbon market prices (e.g., Aslam et al., 2017; Shaikh et al., 2007). The comparisons lead to mixed results dependent on whether the expected carbon prices are sufficient to meet farmers' expectations. However, using fixed payments might make it difficult to reflect the price uncertainty entailed with carbon markets. Two articles account for uncertainty, Canales et al. (2024) include the variation in income as an attribute, while Assaker (2023) analyses hybrid contracts to account for risks entailed in carbon markets.

That payments over carbon markets are result-based is an important difference between the three business models. Both AES and payments over the value chain can also include fixed payments. Considering that the EU prefers result-based payments, it is striking that result-based hypothetical contracts are rarely found. The only exception is Niskanen et al. (2021). Comparing the financial incentives further, the sole article that offers a price premium to participating farmers is the one strongly focused on value chain payments (Weituschat et al., 2023).

That fixed annual payments are more frequently used than result-based or hybrid payments might explain why the incentives 'upfront payments', 'access to credits' and 'sharing of costs' have not been used as a contractual feature so far. However, the fixed per hectare payments leave the question unanswered of how other approaches would be perceived. This is of interest because soil health measures are assumed to pay-off naturally for some farmers in the long run (Canales et al., 2024). Providing farmers with an upfront payment for the initial investment costs may therefore be sufficient. Another reason why this and other incentives might require more detailed attention is, that Kragt et al. (2017) determine via interviews that upfront investment costs are a major hindrance for landowners to engage in carbon farming.

Collective approaches are also analysed in few articles, and part of the incentive category 'Management of the contract'. Latacz-Lohmann et al. (2019) include a collective bonus, while Villanueva et al. (2017) and Assaker (2023) include collective implementation as an attribute that describes who oversees the management of the contract. In this way they intend to display that collective approaches allow the farmers to share fixed costs. Articles on existing carbon farming projects also highlight that collective implementation approaches and the opportunity to share costs can be of high importance for the success of result-based contracts. In result-based contracts, monitoring and other administrative costs are expected to be substantial (Buck &

Palumbo-Compton, 2022; McDonald et al., 2021; Tiusanen et al., 2022). Besides this, the LIFE carbon farming project points out that carbon sequestration can be a completely new challenge for farmers and advice provided by collectives could be essential for successful sequestration (Tiusanen et al., 2022). The other articles in the category 'Management of the contract', e.g., Häfner & Piorr (2021) or Gramig & Widmar (2018) describe whether different entities take any action in the management of the contracts but are not referring to collective management.

Co-benefits from soil health measures have rarely been included in DCE, even though they are described as crucial factors in analyses of farmers' participation decisions in carbon markets or AES (e.g., Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Canales et al., 2024; Kragt et al., 2017; Tiusanen et al., 2022). Buck & Palumbo-Compton (2022) and Cheye (2023) even state that co-benefits are currently the major driver for farmers engaged in carbon farming because carbon markets offer low prices.

Dumbrell et al. (2016) asked Australian farmers to rank the importance of different co-benefits. They find that farmers strongly favour improvements in soil quality, and the reduction of soil erosion. Benefits for biodiversity were also somewhat important and ranked before the opportunity to sell carbon credits and improvements in landscape aesthetics. However, an interesting finding is that in Trenholm et al. (2017) farmers disliked the idea of receiving a sign stating that they work more environmentally friendly and participate in soil health AES. This could show that co-benefits associated with yield increases are considered more important than other sustainability co-benefits and social recognition for them.

Besides this, almost all articles feature multiple measures for soil health. They usually account for most of the attributes used in the experiments. These measures entail different opportunity costs and those with higher costs are usually less liked (Schaub et al., 2023).

Dumbrell et al. (2016) provide a comparison of the measures and asked Australian farmers about their preferences for different carbon farming technologies using a best-worst scaling approach. For mixed crop-livestock farms, they find that there is a preference for leaving stubble after crop harvesting or for implementing rotational grazing. Farmers displayed a dislike for intercropping with perennial pasture, the application of mulch or biochar and the planting of trees. For crop farmers, they find similar results. These farmers would rather leave stubble, and adopt no-till cropping, or apply mulch than to apply biochar or plant trees. Cheye (2023) also describe similar results, farmers willing to engage in carbon credit certification programmes would rather not plant trees or convert areas to grassland to fulfil the requirements. The most preferred measure was conservation tillage, which was preferred over rangeland management.

These preferences are also displayed in the higher willingness-to-accept values for certain measures. Schulze et al. (2023) find that various articles include restrictions on fertilizer use. The authors of these articles determine compensation requests between €30– €670 per hectare and year (Beharry-Borg et al., 2013). Measures for arable farms include crop rotation, intercropping and the use of cover crops. Five articles from Europe provide willingness-to-accept values for these measures. The authors

determined willingness-to-accept values between €4 and €127 per hectare and year (Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2017). Schulze et al.'s (2023) category for soil related measures include tillage restrictions (conservation tillage, reduced tillage). The determined willingness-to-accept values for Europe range from €25-176 per hectare and year (Villanueva et al., 2017; Zandersen et al., 2016). For agroforestry and planting of trees (afforestation), only one article from Austria determined a willingness-to-accept value of €927 per hectare and year. This article investigates farmers' adjustment decisions for climate change and whether AES payments impact these decisions (Pröbstl-Haider et al., 2016).

Another frequently included contractual feature is contract duration. Long contract durations may be necessary because ambitious goals such as carbon sequestration or biodiversity increases require long-term commitments. However, it is described in the review on AES (Schaub et al., 2023) and in the review on contractual features that farmers oppose long-term commitments (Mamine et al., 2020). Harmanny & Schulp (2023) find for the Netherlands that most farmers (57 %) would rather commit to a five-year contract, while only 22% would opt for ten-year contracts, and 21% would prefer even shorter, annual contracts. This is in line with Tiusanen et al. (2022), who find that farmers prefer contracts with 5-10 year long durations. Rochecouste et al. (2017) find in interviews with Australian farmers that farmers do not want to limit their flexibility and the flexibility of successors.

With respect to long term commitments, Buck & Palumbo-Compton (2022) point out that inflation should be considered in future payments. This might help to motivate farmers and overcome commitment issues.

TABLE 3 CONTRACTUAL FEATURES RELEVANT FOR FARMERS' DECISION TO ENGAGE IN THE BUSINESS MODELS

Contractual feature	Sources - AES	Sources – CM	Sources – VCP / others
Incentive – Fixed payment per hectare	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Canales et al., 2024; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Jaeck & Lifran, 2014; Lapierre et al., 2023; Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2019; Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Schulz et al., 2014; Schulze et al., 2023; Stetter & Sauer, 2022; Trenholm et al., 2017; Villanueva et al., 2017; Zandersen et al., 2016)	(Aslam et al., 2017; Assaker, 2023; Canales et al., 2024; Shaikh et al., 2007)	(Beharry-Borg et al., 2013; Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Stetter & Sauer, 2022)
Incentive – Income volatility	(Canales et al., 2024; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Jaeck & Lifran, 2014; Mamine et al., 2020; Stetter & Sauer, 2022)	(Canales et al., 2024)	(Stetter & Sauer, 2022)
Incentive – Expected income / revenue / margin	(Gramig & Widmar, 2018; Jaeck & Lifran, 2014; Levers et al., 2021; Mamine et al., 2020; Stetter & Sauer, 2022)	(Cheye, 2023; Dickinson et al., 2012; Gramig & Widmar, 2018)	(Stetter & Sauer, 2022)
Incentive – Price at farmgate	(Mamine et al., 2020)		
Incentive – Premium price (through eco-labelling)	(Mamine et al., 2020)		(Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Weituschat et al., 2023)
Incentive – Bonus (premium price for quality or quantity)	(Canales et al., 2024; Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2019; Mamine et al., 2020; Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Schulze et al., 2023)		(Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021)
Incentive – Result-based Payment	(Niskanen et al., 2021)	(Assaker, 2023)	
Incentive – Collective bonus (for building network), support to build a network	(Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2019; Mamie et al., 2020; Schulze et al., 2023)		
Incentive - Upfront payment (e.g., investment costs)	(Mamine et al., 2020; Schulze et al., 2023)		
Incentive – Sharing of costs (production costs, specific asset costs)	(Mamine et al., 2020)		
Incentive – Insurance mechanism (e.g., climate change damages)			(Jørgensen et al., 2020)
Incentive – Supply of inputs	(Schulze et al., 2023)		
Incentive – Training and advice	(Lapierre et al., 2023; Mamine et al., 2020; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulze et al., 2023)	(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022)	

Incentive – Access to credit	(Schulze et al., 2023)		
Incentive – Combination with other CAP requirements	(Schulze et al., 2014; Stetter & Sauer, 2022)		(Stetter & Sauer, 2022)
Incentive – Co-benefits (soil fertility, less erosion, water holding capacity etc.)	(Canales et al., 2024; Niskanen et al., 2021)	(Canales et al., 2024)	(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022)
Incentive – Public recognition (e.g. labels, signs)	(Trenholm et al., 2017)		
Commitments - Duration (contract length)	(Gramig & Widmar, 2018; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Jaeck & Lifran, 2014; Lapierre et al., 2023; Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2019; Levers et al., 2021; Mamine et al., 2020; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulze et al., 2023; Stetter & Sauer, 2022; Trenholm et al., 2017; Zandersen et al., 2016)	(Aslam et al., 2017; Dickinson et al., 2012; Gramig & Widmar, 2018)	(Beharry-Borg et al., 2013; Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Stetter & Sauer, 2022)
Commitments - Min. quantity / quality requirement (e.g., hectares enrolled, soil type)	(Mamine et al., 2020; Niskanen et al., 2021; Schulze et al., 2023; Trenholm et al., 2017)		
Commitment – Measures for soil health	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Gramig & Widmar, 2018; Jaeck & Lifran, 2014; Lapierre et al., 2023; Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2019; Niskanen et al., 2021; Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Schulze et al., 2023; Trenholm et al., 2017; Villanueva et al., 2017; Zander & Hamm, 2010)	(Aslam et al., 2017)	(Beharry-Borg et al., 2013; Jørgensen et al., 2020; Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Weituschat et al., 2023)
Others - Flexibility (terminate contracts, option for renegotiation)	(Lapierre et al., 2023; Mamine et al., 2020; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulze et al., 2023; Zandersen et al., 2016)	(Dickinson et al., 2012)	
Others – – Management of the contract (Monitoring, sharing of transaction costs & administrative burden (collective implementation))	(Canales et al., 2024; Gramig & Widmar, 2018; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Mamine et al., 2020; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulze et al., 2023; Villanueva et al., 2017)	(Assaker, 2023; Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Canales et al., 2024; Gramig & Widmar, 2018)	
Others -Information on costs	(Häfner & Piorr, 2021)	(Assaker, 2023)	(Jørgensen et al., 2020)

4.2.2 important personal features

The personal features that might play a role in farmers' decision to participate are in Table 4. In the review by Dessart et al. (2019), these features are intensively discussed. The authors distinguish between dispositional factors, social factors, and cognitive factors. Dispositional factors are stable internal variables like personality, motivations, and beliefs. Social factors refer to farmers' engagement with others, but also include social norms. Cognitive factors relate to learning and knowledge and are assumed to impact farmers' perception of the costs and benefits of measures. In addition to these factors, Schaub et al. (2023) focused on farms' structural features that influence the farmers' opportunity costs. Higher opportunity costs lower farmers' predicted probabilities to participate in a contract.

The table shows that only a few articles analyse the effects of farm and farmer features on the decision to choose a contract for any of the business models. In most cases, only descriptive statistics are presented without providing estimations for subsamples or without including the features in the estimations. Therefore, factors described as relevant in review papers are also added. The articles mostly include features referring to farm structure (farm size measures, management intensities and soil fertility). Other factors that are frequently included are pro-environmental beliefs and socio-demographic variables (age and gender). These variables affect beliefs, while knowledge and education affect farmers' perceptions of costs and benefits (Dessart et al., 2019).

Schaub et al. (2023) highlight the heterogeneity among farmers and farms that leads to heterogeneity of the results. However, for three of the personal features they found consistent results: agricultural education and training opportunities, close relationships to peers and a positive attitude towards AES ('Pro-environmental attitude') increase farmers' willingness to participate in AES. However, Buck & Palumbo-Compton (2022) point out that the literature on soil health practices is too small to draw general conclusions. Still, they point out, that results so far indicate that an awareness of co-benefits is a strong driver of adoption, and that better education and training opportunities can help.

Barreiro-Hurlé et al. (2010) find that farm features and contract features have a stronger importance when very demanding measures are required. When it comes to softer requirements with lower opportunity costs, personal factors play a larger role. Therefore, the measure demanded may determine the strategy to promote it.

TABLE 4 FARM AND FARMERS' FEATURES IDENTIFIED TO BE RELEVANT

Feature	Source – AES	Sources - CM	Sources - VCP, others
Farm structure – current soil management	(Dessart et al., 2019)	(Canales et al., 2024; Shaikh et al., 2007)	(Jørgensen et al., 2020)
Farm structure – Farm size measures	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulz et al., 2014)	(Dickinson et al., 2012)	
Farm structure – Farm profitability / Farmer income	(Levers et al., 2021; Schaub et al., 2023)	(Shaikh et al., 2007)	
Farm structure – Former management intensities (working hours, fertilizer usage, pesticide usage stocking rates, irrigation etc)	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulz et al., 2014; Trenholm et al., 2017; Zandersen et al., 2016)		(Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Weituschat et al., 2023)
Farm structure – Marketing options	(Schaub et al., 2023)		
Farm structure – Rental and purchase prices for farmland	(Schaub et al., 2023)		
Farm structure – Rental agreements		(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022)	
Farm structure – Soil fertility	(Levers et al., 2021; Schaub et al., 2023; Schulz et al., 2014; Trenholm et al., 2017; Zandersen et al., 2016)	(Shaikh et al., 2007)	(Jørgensen et al., 2020)
Farm structure – Farm type (e.g., mixed, dairy, arable)	(Schaub et al., 2023)		(Jørgensen et al., 2020; Schulz et al., 2014)
Farm structure – Production type (organic, conventional)	(Dessart et al., 2019; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Schaub et al., 2023)		
Cognitive – Education & knowledge	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Dessart et al., 2019; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Schaub et al., 2023; Trenholm et al., 2017)	(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Dickinson et al., 2012)	(Weituschat et al., 2023)

Dispositional (proxy) – Gender / Age (affect other features, e.g., beliefs)	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Dessart et al., 2019; Trenholm et al., 2017; Zandersen et al., 2016)	(Dickinson et al., 2012; Shaikh et al., 2007)	(Weituschat et al., 2023)
Social – cluster & peer relationship (information exchange with others e.g., through associations)	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Dessart et al., 2019; Schaub et al., 2023)	(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022)	(Weituschat et al., 2023)
Social – Seeking for technical advice	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010, Häfner & Piorr, 2021)		
Social – Trust in funding source	(Schaub et al., 2023)	(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022)	(Weituschat et al., 2023)
Dispositional – Risk preferences	(Dessart et al., 2019; Schaub et al., 2023)		
Dispositional – Pro-Environmental attitude (experiences with AES, environment related beliefs (e.g., climate change))	Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Dessart et al., 2019; Häfner & Piorr, 2021; Jaeck & Lifran, 2014; Levers et al., 2021; Schaub et al., 2023; Stetter & Sauer, 2022)	(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022)	(Schulz et al., 2014; Stetter & Sauer, 2022; Weituschat et al., 2023)
Dispositional – Business orientation (freedom to operate)	(Dessart et al., 2019; Schaub et al., 2023)	(Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022)	
Dispositional – Extraversion –(Openness towards new experiences)	(Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Dessart et al., 2019)		

4.3 Demand for carbon credits & eco-labelled products

Next, this report will briefly summarize what evidence is available on the demand for carbon credits and consumers' preferences for eco-labelled products.

The LIFE carbon farming project, aimed at developing well-functioning voluntary carbon markets. To identify hindrances, a survey and interviews on carbon markets' feasibility and possible hindrances were conducted. The authors find that buyers expect carbon credits that guarantee permanence, while farmers committed to 20-year contracts only. Buyers pointed out that they do not know what claims would be valid for such short storage periods and, based on this, found the price of €52 per ton too high. Therefore, the project finds a lack of demand for agricultural carbon credits that do not guarantee long storage durations or permanence. A reason for farmers' reluctance to commit to long contracts was stated to be low trust in the partners (Tiusanen et al., 2022).

The Interreg carbon farming project aimed at carbon farming through soil health measures in the North Sea Region. The project set up seven carbon farming projects. The results point out that local offset projects cause substantially higher costs than, for instance, afforestation projects abroad (Demeyer et al., 2022).

On the consumer side, one article assesses Danish consumers' attitudes towards value chain payments for carbon offsets. The authors find that claims are often too confusing and that consumers had little trust in these claims (Haug & Hassinggaard, 2023).

Majer et al. (2022) analyse 26 studies on labels that include economic, environmental, or social aspects. They find that sustainability labelling positively influences consumer behaviour. The authors find that consumer characteristics (pro-environmental attitudes), the characteristics of the purchase situation, and the characteristics of the label play a role. Consumers, for instance, prefer domestic labels, and certification across all production steps. The study also identifies a lack of knowledge and trust as important barriers to consider. Furthermore, it should be noted that the analysed experiments do not allow to predict whether consumers' stated willingness to pay would translate into real purchase decisions.

These sustainability claims are noteworthy, as buyers have the potential to establish initiatives asserting investments in biodiversity or sustainability. This is particularly significant due to the manifold benefits associated with soil health measures, ranging from enhancing animal welfare, landscapes, water quality, to fostering biodiversity. Moreover, certain improvements, such as demonstrating CO₂ reductions or achieving climate neutrality, may pose challenges in verification. Therefore, emphasizing investments in broader sustainability initiatives not only addresses these verification hurdles but also underscores the comprehensive impact of conservation efforts on ecosystems and communities alike.

5 Carbon sequestration potential & marketable products of soil health and other carbon farming measures

Some soil health measure-specific aspects are briefly summarized in this section. Various articles show that the required measures affect farmers' decision to participate in AES, to engage in carbon credit markets or to opt for value chain payments (as shown in Tables 2 - 4). The measures themselves can also be influential as they, for instance, entail different opportunity costs (Schaub et al., 2023) or have a stronger impact on other sustainability objectives, which may attract pro-environmental farmers (Dessart et al., 2019). Furthermore, for farmers interested in carbon markets, sustainability co-benefits and negative effects can be important because activities should at least have a neutral impact. Furthermore, it is assumed that carbon credit certificates from measures that display a positive impact on other sustainability objectives will achieve higher prices (European Commission, 2022b).

The most discussed carbon farming measures on arable land are afforestation and reforestation, agroforestry, soil health measures on arable land, and peatland rewetting (McDonald et al., 2021). All of them are briefly discussed in this section. Besides peatland rewetting, all measures are applicable for land users. Moreover, there is high hope of governments and companies to off-set emissions using carbon credits generated through carbon farming (e.g., Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022). This section will show that some measures can fulfil these expectations better than others. Table 5 presents an overview of all four measures.

Rewetting of peatlands is of specific importance for climate change mitigation. The greenhouse gas emissions from peatlands account for 34% of all agricultural greenhouse gas emissions in the Netherlands and for 15% of the national emissions (Norris et al., 2021). They can only be avoided by rewetting peatlands (Günther et al., 2020).

However, rewetting makes peatlands less or even unusable for farming. Alternative approaches, such as paludiculture, which allows for productive land use of wet and rewetted peatlands that preserves the peat soil (Wetlands International, 2023) or moderately raised water levels that still allow grazing, might allow further usage by farmers (Latacz-Lohmann et al., 2019). Paludiculture, for instance, aims at biomass production for fodder, heating, biofuels, or construction (Wetlands International, 2023). However, if use options are limited, the income forgone for farmers might be especially high for these measures.

TABLE 5 OVERVIEW OF THE SUGGESTED MEASURES, THEIR MONITORING OPTIONS AND THE COSTS INVOLVED (BASED ON COWI ET AL. 2021; McDONALD ET AL. 2021; SCHEID & ITTNER 2022).

	Afforestation	Agroforestry	Soil Health measures on mineral soils	Rewetting of Peatland
Practices	Creation and maintenance of forests	Creation and maintenance of woody features (hedges and trees)	Crop and grassland management (red. tillage, cover crops, fertilizer planning, arable land conversion etc.)	Rewetting, maintenance of peatlands and mire
Sequestration potential (EU wide)	8 - 235 Mt CO ₂ -e/year (Potential per hectare varies with system density, and tree varieties)	8 - 235 Mt CO ₂ -e/year (Potential per hectare varies with system density, and tree varieties)	9 - 70 Mt CO ₂ -e/year for soil health measures, 19 Mt CO ₂ -e/year for fertilizer reducing mgmt. practices	51 - 54 Mt CO ₂ -e/year
Quantification process	Woody biomass on ground (wood carbon code)	Woody biomass on ground (wood carbon code)	Measurement by sampling or by simulation	water tables and vegetation, modelling
Costs (verification and monitoring)	high	high	Modelling medium, measuring very high	Modelling medium, measuring very high
Economic benefits (incentives, marketable products)	wood, carbon credits, ecosystem services	wood, fruits, carbon credits, ecosystem services	Improvements in yields, savings machine / fertilizers, ecosystem services, <u>unlikely carbon credits</u>	carbon credits, ecosystem services,
Co-benefits for the farmer	Reduced soil erosion, on and below ground organic carbon	Reduced soil erosion, improved water capacity, above and below ground organic carbon	Improved water holding capacity, workability of soils, reduced erosion, resilience weather extremes, increase in soil organic carbon	none –often no agricultural usage (Above and below ground carbon)
Co-benefits for society	Biodiversity, water infiltration, landscape improvement	Biodiversity, animal welfare improvements, water infiltration, landscape improvement	Improvements in water quality, on grassland positive effects for biodiversity, landscape improvement	Biodiversity also for aquatic species, flood regulation, water quality, landscape improvement
Potential risks	Negative biodiversity impact when planted e.g., on biodiversity rich grassland	Negative biodiversity impact when planted e.g., on biodiversity rich grassland	Nitrogen releases when organic fertilizers are not applied at right times, adverse effects on biodiversity (no-till)	Methane leakage during rewetting
Assumed scalability (for carbon markets)	Not provided	Great potential	Not possible	Limited area (but highly effective)

The peatland and mire shares per country in the NOVASOIL consortium are shown in Table 6.⁵ They vary highly. Across all countries, it appears that most of the peatlands are not in functioning conditions, peatland in functioning condition is called mire peatland (Tanneberger et al., 2017).

TABLE 6 PEATLAND AND MIRE SHARES OF THE COUNTRIES PARTICIPATING IN THE PROJECT (TANNEBERGER ET AL., 2017).

Country	Country area	Peatland in km ²	Share of peatland (on country area)	Mire in km ²	Share of mire (peatland area)
Bulgaria	110,900	208	0.19%	54	25.96%
Estonia	45,227	9,150	20.23%	3,250	35.52%
Germany	357,137	12,800	3.58%	250	1.95%
Italy	301,339	750	0.25%	120	16.00%
Latvia	64,562	7,514	11.64%	3,165	42.12%
Netherlands	37,354	2,733.4	7.32%	150	5.49%
Spain	505,992	350	0.07%	200	57.14%
United Kingdom	242,495	26,838.3	11.07%	8,750	32.60%

Soil health measures might be better liked by farmers because they allow the continuation of agricultural production on the land. However, soil carbon sequestration on arable land faces the challenge that it is fully reversible by tilling after periods of no-till and that it is impacted by natural conditions such as droughts, floods, and fires. Moreover, long-term storage will be essential to mitigate climate change (Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Paul et al., 2023). Conversely, reductions per hectare in other measures predominantly hinge on factors such as tree density and the specific tree species employed in afforestation or agroforestry endeavors (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021)

Something that all measures have in common is that they entail high costs for monitoring effectiveness. However, multiple projects work on monitoring methods and costs could reduce in the future (Springer, 2023). Co-benefits were identified as crucial factors when it came to farmers' adoption decisions. Furthermore, they might be of importance for carbon credit generation. Table 5 thus also holds an overview of the co-benefits and potential risks these measures hold. A review by Scheid et al. (2023) on the co-effects shows both negative and positive effects. Comparing the measures shows that afforestation, agroforestry, and peatland rewetting perform better than soil health measures (McDonald et al., 2021). An example of a negative co-effect of carbon farming is described in Barbato & Strong (2023). They find that some farmers have doubts about whether carbon market approaches are beneficial for biodiversity. They state that some contracts for no-till in the US are specifically made to fit large-scale,

⁵ Peatland actively forming peat and sequestering additional carbon is called mire.

monoculture farms. Furthermore, farmers expressed concerns that large seed and herbicide companies could seek to tailor carbon farming to their needs which could make farmers more dependent on their products.

While the quantification process for EU certified credits is still undergoing development, certain measures with significant potential for carbon storage and positive co-benefits for biodiversity are already being identified for prioritisation. Notably, carbon storage in peat soils, reforestation, and agroforestry are emerging as highly promising alternatives, both in terms of their scalability and environmental impact (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021). However, it's worth noting that soil health measures are currently subject to critical evaluation (Paul et al., 2023).

6 Discussion & Conclusion

The EU seeks to promote soil health measures to secure our food provision but also to mitigate climate change (European Commission, 2023b). Soil health measures require adjustments in farm management and farmers usually expect a remuneration to implement them. This report focused on the three main business models to promote soil health measures on farms (public payments through the CAP, private payments through carbon credit markets, and private payments through the value chain) and summarized the existing literature on these business models.

In deliverable 1.1 of the NOVASOIL project, the following factors were determined to be decisive for success: environmental effectiveness, fairness for the involved parties (distribution of costs and benefits), compliance with the legal framework and acceptance. This section points out the potential success of the business models and what could be of interest for upcoming research on these business models.

Environmental effectiveness

Numerous articles, for instance, Bartkowski et al. (2021), Burton & Schwarz (2013), and Matzdorf et al. (2008), argue that result-based instead of action-based payments hold potential to improve the environmental effectiveness of measures. Carbon markets provide purely result-based payments. Payments over the CAP are mostly action-based, even though the EU states to prefer result-based approaches (COWI et al., 2021, McDonald et al., 2021). For payments over the value chain existing approaches often seem to include hybrid payments (Demeyer et al., 2022).

There are reasons why purely result-based payments can be viewed critically when it comes to soil health measures that aim at carbon storage. First, farmers will have to wait for at least five years until some carbon has built up to allow a remuneration via result-based approaches (Demeyer et al., 2022). Whether farmers will be willing to apply and pre-finance the measures is questionable. Existing research projects found that hybrid or action-based schemes that provide fixed remunerations are preferred by farmers (section 4.2). Second, action-based contracts may be necessary for farmers with already high carbon content in their soils. Since carbon only increases to certain thresholds in soils, purely result-based contracts will not be able to provide incentives to these farmers (Demeyer et al., 2022). Moreover, because these farmers cannot sequester additional carbon, they may be unattractive participants in carbon markets and value chain payments. This may especially apply when high carbon contents are determined by regional factors and, therefore, included in the regional-specific baseline (Section 3.2) or when carbon sequestration is determined for individual farms.

Fairness for the involved parties

Fairness for the involved parties requires consideration for all business models. For AES that seek to become result-based it should be considered that, as stated, those farmers with already high carbon content need to be included. In addition, researchers on result-based AES should consider that even though soil health measures increase carbon content, that content varies with factors outside the farmers' control such as temperature, fire or heavy rains. Thresholds to reach payments should account for these factors.

When researching value chain payments, asymmetries in market power need consideration to avoid that farmers are not sufficiently compensated (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022). In addition, it might also be of interest to consider that the claimed carbon off-sets need to be reliable and that, otherwise, liability questions arise (section 3.2). How to reach a fair distribution of leakage risks for value chain payments and carbon markets might also be of interest, especially for risks outside of the farmers' control.

Compliance with the legal framework

Whether soil health measures can comply with legal frameworks is in question when carbon offsets are sold over carbon markets. Even though the quantification process for EU-certified credits is still in its development, indications exist that carbon storage in rewetted peat soils, through reforestation, and agroforestry will be preferred (McDonald et al., 2021). Soil health measures, on the other hand, are critically viewed because of problems with reversibility and permanence (Paul et al., 2023). Rather than through carbon credit markets, soil health measures can be stimulated through payments in the value chain.

However, when value chain actors consider using carbon offsets of their suppliers to state climate neutrality, they will, in the future, have to prove that these claims are justified (section 3.3). For this reason, it remains questionable whether they can claim reductions of CO₂ or even climate neutrality. Nevertheless, it might be easier for the value chain to prove CO₂ reductions in a reliable way compared to farmers selling carbon credits. This is because farmers must maintain the carbon on relatively small areas and the credits may be bound to one specific activity. For value chain actors, it can be easier to reliably prove reductions across all their suppliers because multiple measures can be combined (e.g., in barns and on arable land), and large numbers of farmers can be included. Large numbers of farmers and the combination of multiple measures most likely reduce the variation in offsets. Unfortunately, research on value chain payments for ecosystem services so far appears to be scarce (section 4.2).

When working on the business models that remunerate offsets, researchers will have to pay attention to the implementation of AES and eco-schemes in their home countries. This is necessary to ensure the additionality of offsets.

Acceptance

In surveys, consumers displayed a preference for claims such as 'climate neutrality'. Whether they are also willing to pay price premiums for products that may not be able to use strong claims is unknown. This might be necessary when companies cannot reliably prove the offset. In these cases, companies might only be able to state that they incentivize farmers to provide ecosystem services.

On the farmers' side, research indicates that farmers prefer action-based payments over result-based payments (section 4.2). This should be considered when working on AES and payments over the value chain. Both could include action-based remunerations (hybrid or purely action-based). Furthermore, it is found that farmers dislike committing their land for long periods of time and implementing more demanding measures (e.g., afforestation, agroforestry, and peatland rewetting). This is

especially problematic for payments for carbon sequestration. Carbon takes time to sequester and should be stored long-term to contribute to climate change mitigation (European Commission, 2022b).

On the buyers' side, value chain actors expressed concerns about relatively short commitment periods and whether they can make claims based on this. Whether consumers find weaker claims attractive is likely to influence companies' willingness to offer payments for ecosystem services to farmers. In case that consumers respond also to weaker claims, shorter periods of commitment might not be that problematic. Shorter periods might still allow to improve soil health, even though contributions to climate change mitigation may be limited. In case that consumers are not willing to pay for weaker claims on soil health improvements, researchers could focus on how to build trust between contract partners. This might increase farmers' willingness to accept longer contracts.

Furthermore, one research project found that buyers might not be willing to pay high carbon prices that would be necessary for the more expensive European carbon credits (Demeyer et al., 2022). However, buyers' interest might be influenced by consumers' willingness to pay for European offsets and also deserves attention.

Success of the business models

Considering these factors, it is difficult to determine whether there is a single business model that is the most promising. However, considering the legislative framework, it becomes clear that soil health measures should not be promoted for carbon markets.

A more promising alternative would be to further develop existing AES or eco-schemes. They are an important funding source, but their efficiency (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021) and their use rates among farmers need improvement (Zimmermann & Britz, 2016). When working on AES payments, it might be worth considering the development of existing schemes further. This helps to avoid confusion among farmers when more and more eco-schemes or AES would be created, and is, for instance, also suggested by COWI et al. (2021).

In addition, researchers could explore the acceptance of value chain payments by farmers. As the literature review showed, little is known on about this topic but value chain payments hold potential for multiple reasons:

- i) large-scale companies need to reach climate neutrality by 2050, which could increase their interest in these contracts (Runge, Langlais, et al., 2022),
- ii) private contracts are flexible, farmers could be motivated by making payments partly action-based, by offering trainings or meetings with peers,
- iii) contracts over the value chain ensure that there is a buyer for the offsets,
- iv) in case that acceptance rates remain low, companies can make the commitment to measures mandatory for suppliers.

All of these aspects could help to scale up the measures and improve soil health and carbon sequestration in larger areas.

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